

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

Google Scholar

SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Yangiboyev.B.

SIGIRLARDA KATTA QORIN ASIDOZINING SABABLARI,

DAVOLASH VA OLDINI OLISH CHORALARI (TAHLIL NATIJALARI)

DRJI

Universal
Impact Factor

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

zenodo

ADVANCED SCIENCE INDEX

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

2023-2024

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ